

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B158
Date: 17 Jan 2006
Take Off 08:54:20
Landing: 13:41:02
Flight Time 4h46m42

Campaign: DABEX: north-south sampling biomass burning plumes

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area:

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Simon Osborne	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	Core Chemistry	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	CVI	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	CCN / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	Filters	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	SWS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office
12	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
13	Mission scientist 2	Jim Haywood	Met Office
14	Wet Neph	Martin Glew	Met Office
15	IIR / Bags	Joss Kent	Met Office
16			

Flight Track:

B158 Track 17-JAN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b158
 Date: 17 Jan 2006
 Project: DABEX
 Location: Niamey to Ilorin

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
082413		Position	0.77 kft	109	13'28.65N, 2'10.53E
085420		T/O	1.5 kft	089	Niamey
085651		ASPs	4.3 kft	176	Open
090056	090409	Profile 1	5.0 - 2.3 kft	290	2.3K'
090620	090847	Profile 1	2.3 - 0.84 kft	092	2.3K'- 50' over NIA
090848	091608	Profile 2	0.82 - 5.0 kft	090	500fpm
091236		Videos	3.2 kft	132	FFC & UFC
091618	092356	Profile 2	5.1 - 13.0 kft	128	1000fpm from FL50
092443	093010	Profile 2	13.0 - 18.0 kft	128	
093010	093831	Profile 3	18.0 - 10.0 kft	133	
093831	094605	Run 1	10.0 kft	125	To Point A
094720	095103	Profile 4	10.0 - 6.0 kft	176	
095104	095215	Run 2	6.0 kft	179	
095300	101303	Run 3	6.5 kft	179	
100433		Bag 134	6.5 kft	177	Start filling
101304	102044	Profile 5	6.5 - 2.8 kft	177	500fpm to 2.8k'
102045	102631	Run 4	2.8 kft	181	Q1013
102225		Bag 130	2.8 kft	180	Start filling
102632	103112	Profile 6	2.8 - 5.0 kft	179	Q1013 500fpm
103113	104449	Run 5	5.0 kft	177	Cu below, End Ilorin
103210		Bag 93	5.0 kft	178	Start filling
104540		Videos	5.0 kft	176	Change tapes
104838	104936	Orbit 1	4.5 - 4.4 kft	253	60deg right from 290
105047	105141	Orbit 2	4.6 kft	034	60deg right, 040
105232	105325	Orbit 3	4.6 - 4.5 kft	134	60deg right, 150
105407	105508	Orbit 4	4.6 - 4.4 kft	217	60deg right, 230
105650	105852	Profile 7	4.5 - 6.0 kft	001	500fpm
105853	110854	Run 6	6.0 kft	355	500fpm
110854	111109	Profile 8	6.0 - 8.0 kft	357	1000fpm
111110	111411	Run 7.1	8.0 kft	356	
111603	112656	Run 7.2	8.0 kft	181	for AMS
112340		Bag 54	8.0 kft	177	Start filling
113100	113317	Profile 9	8.0 - 10.0 kft	355	1000fpm
113524	113637	Profile 10	10.0 - 9.0 kft	177	No aerosol at FL100
113638	114456	Run 8	9.0 kft	176	End @ Ilorin
113735		Bag 74	9.0 kft	176	Start filling
114737	115622	Profile 11	9.0 - 18.0 kft	356	
115829	121240	Profile 12	18.0 - 5.0 kft	358	1000fpm to FL50
121300	121303	Profile 12	4.9 - 4.8 kft	000	500fpm
121317	121832	Profile 12	4.7 - 2.0 kft	000	
121832	123930	Run 9	2.0 kft	359	Q1013
121916		Videos	2.0 kft	001	Change tapes
122535		Event	2.0 kft	000	Fire @122535 on DFC
122752		Heimann	2.0 kft	000	Cal, 30-40deg
124016	124459	Profile 13	2.0 - 5.0 kft	308	500fpm
124500	125501	Run 10	5.0 kft	305	
125501	125908	Profile 14	5.0 - 9.0 kft	319	
125908	130908	Run 11	9.0 kft	319	
130908	131823	Profile 15	9.0 - 18.0 kft	318	1000fpm
131823	132818	Profile 16	18.0 - 8.1 kft	261	1000fpm
133010	133314	Profile 16	6.8 - 5.1 kft	074	1000fpm to FL50
133323	133624	Profile 16	4.9 - 2.4 kft	067	500fpm to 2.3k' Q1013
134102		Land	0.88 kft	108	Niamey
134640		Position	0.88 kft	123	13'28.66N, 2'10.53E

B158 Track 17-JAN-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DABEX: north-south sampling biomass burning plumes

Flight No: B158

Date: 17 January 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling at various altitudes of the mineral dust to the south of Niamey towards Ilorin where biomass burning aerosol will dominate.

Location:

Over land area between Niamey (13.54°N, 2.66°E) and Ilorin to the south (8°19'N, 4°20'E).

Weather:

High loadings of biomass burning aerosol. Cloudless skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Missed approach (50ft) over Niamey airfield and low-level (500ft) flying over land.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Niamey.
2. Ascend to 5000ft and carry out a missed approach descent to 50ft over Niamey airfield [15mins, T=15mins]
3. Profile ascent from 50ft to FL150 (or above the dust layer), at a rate of 500ft/min below FL050 and 1000ft/min above FL050 towards 12°N, 4°20'E [20mins, T=35mins]
4. SLR at FL120 until point 12°N, 4°20'E is reached [20mins, T=55mins]
5. Set of three SLRs due south at ~FL090, ~FL060, 2000ft to reach Ilorin [50mins, T=105mins]
6. Set of four orbits at 600ft (bank angle 50°) over Ilorin AERONET site [15mins, T=120mins]
7. Stacked profile ascent with 10 min SLRs at five different altitudes to be advised by the aircraft scientist (suggest 500ftAGL, 4000ft, FL070, FL100 and FL120) [60mins, T=180mins]
8. SLRs towards Banizoumbou via point 12°N, 4°20'E at various altitudes between 2000ft and FL150 to be advised by the aircraft scientist [70mins, T=250mins]
9. Profile descent from FL150 to 500ft over Banizoumbou at a rate of 1000ft/min above FL050 and at 500ft/min below this [20mins, T=270mins]
10. Land at Niamey.

Aircraft Scientist de-brief sheet

Flight B158

17th January 2006

3rd DABEX sortie

Summary of the weather:

Frontal-type band of cirrus moving with the jet to the NW of Niamey; this shed cirrus strands to the south. Wispy cirrus around the Niamey area; clear skies at high level to the south over the operating region (Ilorin). Found low level cumulus field upon arrival at Ilorin. Some dust to the north of Niamey. NAME model indicating heavy biomass burning aerosol advecting at low and high level in a NEly flow over the Atlantic and Gulf of Guinea.

Geographical points defined for the flight:

Point A: 12°N, 4°20'E.

Point B: 8°19N, 4°20'E (Ilorin)

Banizoumbou: 13°32'N, 02°40'E

Summary of the flight:

A very successful sortie was carried out to sample biomass burning aerosol plumes on a north-south line from point A to point B (Ilorin AERONET site), plus some in-situ and radiation work over point B. This latter work was somewhat scuppered by low level cumulus clouds, which meant coincident comparisons with AERONET data will not be possible. But skies were cloud free above the aircraft.

A missed approach was first carried out over Niamey airfield down to 50ft. Two distinct aerosol layers were seen during the profile (P2) to FL180. Aerosol was still present to almost this altitude, although there was a gradual decrease in concentration above FL110. A profile descent was then carried out to FL100 where a run was maintained until point A. Ci cloud thinned out during the run to zero at point A. PCASP concs were ~300/cc during the run. After point A, a profile descent was made to FL065 where PCASP concs rose to ~3500/cc. A SLR was performed at FL065 heading due south towards point B. Good hits were also seen on the NO_x and NO₂. SID was recording predominantly spherical particles. There was a gradual increase in neph scattering along the run. A profile descent to 2800ft reveal No_x at 8ppb and CO to 800 ppbv, but also a cumulus humulus field at this height. A run was made at this height, where there were numerous cloud penetrations. The run was cut short and a climb was made to FL050. 4/8 cloud was observed from this altitude below. During this run (R5) the AMS dropped out but was re-booted successfully (approx 15 mins of data lost). After R5, point B was reached and a series of four orbits was carried at above the cumulus field (now 7-8/8 cloud cover) at a height of 4500ft. The bank angle was 60°. Ascertaining Ci cover was not really possible due to the turbid atmosphere above us at the time. A stacked profile ascent was then carried out with SLRs at the following levels:

- FL060 within heavy aerosol (PCASP~3500/cc)

- FL080 within heavy aerosol
- FL090 initially in a 'clear slot' but came into aerosol later in run (i.e. uneven top to aerosol layer)

The profile climb was continued to FL180; during this climb THREE distinct aerosol layers could be observed. The highest layer was at about FL134. At this height we could see some cirrus, but not directly above. We feel the measurements at lower level over Ilorin were cloud free above. A profile descent was then made from FL180 to 2000ft. The three aerosol layers were observed very nicely during this descent. A low level run (2000ft) was carried out heading north towards point A. The sky was totally clear of cloud during this run. Fire were also observed, with some flaming (at ~122500z, maybe captured on the DFC). Visibility was no greater than 6km at the altitude. Massive aerosol plumes were encountered during this run. A profile climb was then made to FL050 (a clear slot) where a SLR was carried out. The next run was at FL090, where concentrations started fairly low and increased along the run. High level cloud had increased by now; this seemed to be various types of Ci at different heights. A profile was made to FL180 and then back down to 2300ft in the vicinity of Banizoumbou. The top of the aerosol was at around FL145 with a gradual increase with decreasing height.

Instrument status:

SWS and SHIMS working ok, but not together at the same time. SHIMS was used predominantly except for orbits, a short period at 2000ft heading north to spectrally characterise the surface, and later when Ci cloud hampered downwelling radiation.

Wet neph: system recording ok and functionality fine. However: (i) wet to dry ratio of scatter coeffs approx 0.9 when no humidification- i.e. should be unity; (ii) data in flight showed no growth with humidity. This is surprising as biomass burning aerosol should deliquesce quite measurably. Dry neph signal looked fine throughout flight.

AMS: drop out and loss of data for a short (~15 min) period around 103600z.

Bag sampling carried out.

CCN fine; some maxing out of supersaturation spectra at 0.1-0.2 % !!

CVI PCASP reading greater than CVI CPC and wing-mounted PCASP. Probably due to small channel electronic noise.

S.R. Osborne
18th January 2006

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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Date17/01/06.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0854					T/O NIAMEY AIRFIELD. Wispers of ^{→ actually 4-6/8 cover} 2 above.
		VIS < 5km?			reasonable haze about.
		4400'			white appearance to scattering E-climb to F050 // dark layer to left of us.
090040		F2050		preparing for descent	
090054	P1 ↓	F050	290	13.2° 2.0E	Start profile descent over airfield 2 aerosol layers seen from this level
090250	P1 ↓				Restart (?) descent @ 1000ft/min.
090406	P1 →	2300'	075	13.4° 2.0E	Intermittent profile descent increasing aerosol @ ~2300' (lower haze layer)
090620	P1 ↓	2300'	092		Re-start profile descent.
090846	P1 ↓	50'	090	13.4° 2.1E	End descent / Start profile ascent climb rate ~ 700ft/min? SURK NIAMEY AIRFIELD. less Ci ahead now?
091076		~2000'			climb rate variable. turning also in climb.
091218		~3000'			v. hazy + white now ahead
091304		~3500'			can see dark band ahead.
		~4200'			into dark slot a neph dropp?
091607		5500'			change to 1000ft/min - Hitting 2nd aerosol layer! Organic or AMS.
		~7000'			Not - aged → AMS

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
091906		8000'	126		TD mistering with light. $w_0 = 0.7$ w_0 ^{unclear} !! very absorbent
		10,000'			mark constant with height!
0922		FL110			curving out of top.
		FL122			descent rising again - can't see ground yet.
092254	P2 →	FL130	129	12.9 N 2.9 E	Interrupt while ascent -
092442	P2 →	FL130	128		Restart climb -
					3-4/8 Ci above
		FL155			RASP ~ 80/c.
093010	P2 N	FL180	133	12.6 3.3	End climb / start prof descent. Ci thinning - but "Ci" type cloud on horizon to left???
093419		FL159			In haze again; cannot see cloud. Sensd.
		FL105			vertical structure different here v. hazy all around.
093830	P2 ↳ P1	FL100	125	12.3 N 5.8 E	End profile / start run. RASP ~ 300/c. $w_0 = 0.5$!! not too extensive.
					can see 'blbs' of cloud @ 4 o'clock
094160		FL100			But totally clear above now.
094604	P1	FL100	126	12.0 4.2	Prof Run.
094717	P3 ↓	FL100	126	12.0 4.2	Start profile descent ^{1000ft/min}
0949		Good	127	11.8 4.2	Can see rising rapidly now. con ~ 450 → 400pph. RASP ~ 350/c.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
095104					End profile / start SLR
09520					End run, & climb back into aerosol.
095258	R2	FL865	179	11.6 4.2	End climb & start SLR. FL865 03 ~ peak @ 89 ppb.
0955					No cloud seen now. Very very hazy
095601					Cones decreasing. Cocci complete
0957		FL865			Can just see ground below. SHIMS only → looks like PCASP ~ 3800/cc Excellent!!
100305		FL865			Very poor VIS → 2.5 ppb. NO2/NOx All counters Increasing.
100632					Bag filled during run. PCASP ~ 4000/cc (SD) ~ 80-90/sec mostly spherical particles (SD).
101100		FL865	(178)	10.4 4.9	Gradual increase in ^{OSP} aerosol along Run. live PCASP 6000 → 7000cc !!
101301	R2 / PS1	FL865	177	10.3 4.3	End run / Start profile descent ↳ PCASP / real counting cones at very end of run. con ~ 800+ ppb. NOx ~ 8 ppb?
	PS1	FL865	179.		(Bundling surface) ← Peak in aerosol 5000' ? at low cones here. 1/8 sec about
101946		4000'			Con → lift Con / humidity.
101950		3300'			Peak into aerosol.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1020	PSL / 04	2800'			End profile (start SLR at cloud height. Flies about on ground.
		2800'	181		In/out of Cu/hc (PSAP off)
102229					Bag filled
102620	16A PS →	2800'	181	7.4 N 4.3 E	end run. Start profile to much cloud. 500/mi. seen.
					Cu tops ~ 3000 ft to be safe.
103113		Fl050	177	7.1/4.3	End profile (climb & start run.
		Fl050		7.1/4.3	4/9 Cu here below us now.
103210		Fl050			Bag #3 filled. Good placement start of run
103600		Fl050			Ames gone down ??? No CCP also
1043	→	Fl050	177	8.4/4.3	Top of Cu below us now.
10448	PS	Fl050	175	8.7/4.3	End run. Dsp ~ 500x10 ⁶ m ⁻¹ . More depth to cloud here?
104600					Dropping in height. 6-7/8 cu cover. Holding at 4500 for orbit
		Fl045			Scin lots of aerosol about.
104832	01	Fl045		8.0/4.3	Start orbit. RH down. Over
104934	01	Fl045			End orbit. No obvious cloud above
					Almost total cloud cover below us.
105044	02	~4600'		8.1/4.3	Start orbit. RH down.
105139	02				End orbit.
105230	03	~4550'			Start orbit. contact a certain di.
105325	03	~4400'		8.1/4.3	End orbit.
109409	04	4500'			Start orbit.

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	04	4600'			End start . (last one!!)
105501					end!! → own wake?
105506		4600'			End start.
105649	R7.1	4500'	001	8.2/4.3	Start profile climb. 500 ft/min
105851	R6	6000'	355	8.2/4.3	End climb / Start SLR
110200	R6	6000'			Percep ~ 3700 c. CO cal ^{at} at start. (CO cal gas value ~ 525 ppb)
110420		6000'			1-2/8 cu below wa. - above now.
					CO ~ 600 ppbv. in smoke. CO ~ 500 ppbv. early. Fairly steady gas + aerosol concs.
110854	R6 R6.1	6000'			End SLR + start climb. concs rising.
111109	R7.1	FL080	357	9.1/4.2	End climb. / Start SLR. Can see blue sky above → no cloud? cannot see surface from here.
111412	R7.1	FL080	357	9.3/4.2	End SLR to turn winds 15kts @ 180°.
111602	R7.2	FL080	181	9.3/4.2	Start turn. Concs about the same as FL080, maybe a little lower. White out in all dirs. CUE OPC ~ 8000 c noise? PERSP ~ 4500 c. EXCELLENT!!
					CHANGE NOISE! CUE OPC > CUE CNC.
112340		FL080			BAG FILLED.
112651	R7.2	FL080	176	8.6/4.2	End turn. Wet veg not showing any growth at all.

system working
OK, though

$\frac{W}{D} \approx 0.90$

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
113100	P9 ↗	FL080	356	8.2/43	Start profile ascent.
113316	P9	FL000	.		end profile → out of aerosol.
113525	P10 ↓	FL100			Start descent back into the haze
113635	P10 /	FL090	176	8.8/43	End descent ^{of it} & start of SLR.
113830					Some Ci to our right near
113735					BAG FILLED. Can see clear
	→ in <u>dear slot?</u>				maybe affect rad: ^{slot} work
	↳ can see band				out of window.
114215		FL090			Hitting some aerosol now.
					↳ <u>unseen top to aerosol(?)</u>
114650		FL090	176	8.3/43	End Pass in reasonable descent.
114736	P11 ↗	FL090	356	8.7/44	Start profile (limits).
		FL110			Strin in pollution → but dropping off.
115149		FL135			Aerosol comes dropping off also CO, O3 ...
					<u>Fantastic</u> dear slot out of window.
115328					wisps of thin Ci to the left.
115400					Can see partic aerosol layers on the nose?!!
115619	P11 .	FL180	000	9.0/43	End profile ascent.
					cannot see ground. Ci to left; dear to right & straight ahead.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
115827	P12 ↓	FL180	358	9.1/4.3	Start mobile descent. 3 aerosol layers again. FL150 → ^{aerosol} top layer, v. thin.
120340	P12 ↓	FL134			Nothing next layer of aerosol? No Ci above.
		12200'	o-captain altitude		next peak (2 ^m from top of profile)
120720		10,000'			Drooping lanes.
		7600'			→ next increase in real scatter.
120900		8,400'			cannot see surface - bumpy.
121021		7200'			Whiting landscape turbidity inc. Brownish haze to vis out of window
		5,500'			Peak of aerosol. PARS ~ 6500/cc.
121241		4000'	001	10.2/4.3	to 500 ft/mi. ⁸¹⁶⁵ winds @ 203°.
		3600'			Can see ground now.
		2000'			v. strong hydrokapee 0.1500m.
121829	P12 → P9	2000'	000	10.6/4.3	End profile descent / Start Run. No wind Around.
					Lots of signs of past burning
					(SWS looking down) Co ~ 500 ppb. ¹⁰⁻⁵⁵ Tsp ~ 550
122500		2000'			Flicking Flies to our right ¹¹¹ x 10 ⁻⁶ mi ⁻¹ pollution increase → <u>MASSIVE</u>
					(co-pilot query) VIS ~ 6km (?).
123150		2000'			clouds FREE still.
					5-6 mins of run.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
123925	R9	2000'	000°	11.9/4.3	End Run. @ Point A. turn to level for Bestizumbo.
124016	P13	2000' ↑	307	11.9/4.3	Start profile ascent. Some structure, drop Δ = Δ in ascent.
	P13 / P10	FL050			End profile ascent / Start SER. In a clear slot ↓ May as well stay here → fairly interesting.
125459	P10 / P11	FL050	318	12.5/3.5	End Run - (?) about now. & climb to next level.
		FL060			peak ? in next. lots of li above.
125908			319	12.7/3.3	End prof climb / start SER. Even lower ones here; CO ~ 200 ppbv. gone over to SW during this Run ∴ it too much cloud above.
130624		FL090			cones gradually increasing during run.
130909	P11 / P15	FL090	317	13.2/2.9	End run / start profile ascent extent
131240		FL130			avoid dropping, then another little peak. Can see strat/paki from the window.
131320					(turning left in climb) pretty much 8/8 cover here
		FL150			low cones now / CO ~ 128 ppbv.
131821	P15A / P16	FL180	261	13.4/2.3	End profile climb / start prof. drop A few high cloud types above. Co different kinds of ?
132150		FL145			Need start to increase. In ascent layer proper now.
		FL130			

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B158

Date: 17/1/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
09:00:58	500	0.10	Off	20	10											Start Profile 1 from FL050	
09:01:55	140	0.11	Off	30	20											FL040	
09:03:10	200	0.12	Off	50	30											FL030	
09:06:46	210	0.14	Off	80	70											FL020	
09:08:49	440	0.11	Off	70	50											End of Profile 1 & Start Profile 2 @ 50'	
09:10:39	210	0.15	Off	70	50											FL020	
09:12:20	170	0.14	Off	50	35											FL030	
09:14:30	180	0.14	Off	10	10											FL040	
09:16:10	240	0.11	Off	20	65											FL050	
09:17:10	1000	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL060	
09:18:20	500	0.11	Off	10	Noise											FL070	
09:18:59	470	0.11	46	10	Noise											FL080	
09:19:52	425	0.11		5	Noise											FL090	
09:20:51	425	0.12		5	Noise											FL100	
09:21:55	105	0.10		5	Noise											FL110	
09:22:56	280	0.10		5	Noise											FL120	
09:23:54	200	0.09		5	Noise											FL130	
09:25:59	120	0.09		2	Noise											FL140	
09:27:00	100	0.09		2	Noise											FL150	
09:28:13	65	0.09		2	Noise											FL160	
09:29:06	55	0.09		2	Noise											FL170	
09:30:07	25	0.09		2	Noise											End of Profile 2 & Start Profile 3 @ FL180	
09:31:03	60	0.08		1	Noise											FL170	
09:32:10	420	0.11		5	Noise											FL160	
09:33:13	480	0.11		5	Noise											FL150	
09:34:19	670	0.11		5	Noise											FL140	
09:35:09	490	0.11		5	Noise											FL130	
09:36:11	110	0.10		5	Noise											FL120	
09:37:12	300	0.11		5	Noise											FL110	
09:38:31	340	0.11		5	Noise											End of Profile 3 & Start Run 1 @ FL100	
09:39:00	330	0.11		5	Noise												
09:41:00	300	0.11		5	Noise												
09:43:00	250	0.11		5	Noise												
09:45:00	300	0.10		5	Noise												
09:46:06																End of Run 1	
09:47:21	350	0.10		5	Noise											Start Profile 4 from FL100	
09:48:16	780	0.10		5	10											FL090	
09:49:12	2000	0.10		10	10											FL080	
09:50:05	3000	0.11		80	50											FL070	
09:51:07																End of Profile 4 & Start Run 2 @ FL060	
09:52:15																End of Run 2	
09:53:00	3400	0.09	47	60	50											Start Run 3 @ FL065	
09:55:00	2800	0.09		60	50												
09:57:00	3600	0.09	48	50	50												
09:59:00	3000	0.09	49	50	50												
10:01:00	3000	0.09	50	50	50												

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B158

Date: 17/1/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:03:00	3000	0.10	Off	80	70												
10:05:00	3300	0.10	Off	80	70												
10:07:00	3100	0.10	50	80	80												
10:09:00	3500	0.10		70	55												
10:11:00	4500	0.10	52	80	70												
10:13:05																End of Run 3 @ Start of Profile 5 from FL065	
10:14:09	6000	0.11	54	80	80											FL060	
10:16:23	6000	0.11	Off	90	55											FL050	
10:18:25	4200	0.10	Off	90	50											FL040	
10:20:45																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 4 @ 2800'	
10:21:00	3000	0.10	56	70	35												
10:23:00	2700	0.10	58	50	25												
10:25:00	2900	0.10	121	100	30												
10:26:28																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 6	
10:29:20	4400	0.11	Off	80	50											FL040	
10:31:14																End of Profile 6 & Start Run 5 @ FL050	
10:32:00	6300	0.11	Off	90	55												
10:34:00	4300	0.11	Off	80	40												
10:36:00	4400	0.10	Off	80	45												
10:38:00	4200	0.11	Off	80	50												
10:40:00	4000	0.10	Off	80	35												
10:42:00	4100	0.10	Off	80	40												
10:44:50																End of Run 5	
10:48:41																Start Orbits @ FL045	
10:55:08																End of Orbits	
10:56:52	4300	0.10	Off	100	35											Start Profile 7 from FL045	
10:57:35	3900	0.10	Off	90	Noise											FL050	
10:58:54																End of Profile 7 & Start Run 6 @ FL060	
10:59:00	3600	0.11	Off	80	Noise												
11:01:00	4400	0.11	Off	80	Noise												
11:03:00	3300	0.11	Off	80	Noise												
11:05:00	3500	0.11	Off	80	Noise												
11:07:00	4000	0.12	Off	80	40												
11:08:55																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 8 from FL060	
11:10:03	4300	0.12	Off	90	55											FL070	
11:11:10																End of Profile 8 & Start Run 7.1 @ FL080	
11:12:00	3500	0.11	666	70	35												
11:14:00	4000	0.11		80	35												
11:14:11																End of Run 7.1	
11:16:04																Start Run 7.2 @ FL080	
11:17:00	3800	0.11	667	80	Noise												
11:19:00	3800	0.11	668	80	1												
11:21:00	4100	0.11		80	1												
11:23:00	3900	0.11	Off	50	Noise												
11:25:00	3900	0.11	Off	50	Noise												
11:27:00																End of Run 7.2	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B158

Date: 17/1/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
11:31:01	4000	0.11	Off	80												Start Profile 9 from FL080	
11:32:15	1200	0.10		20												FL090	
11:33:16	1100	0.10		10												End of Profile 9 @ FL100	
11:35:24																Start Profile 10 from FL100	
11:36:38																End of Profile 10 & Start Run 8 @ FL090	
11:37:00	1300	0.10	Off	20	Noise												
11:39:00	1400	0.10	Off	20	Noise												
11:41:00	1400	0.10	670	20	1												
11:43:00	2400	0.11		30	1												
11:44:57																End of Run 8	
11:47:38																Start profile 11 from FL090	
11:48:52	1500	0.11		20	10											FL100	
11:49:44	1300	0.11		20	5											FL110	
11:50:39	830	0.11		10												FL120	
11:51:37	320	0.10		5												FL130	
11:52:27	100	0.10		2												FL140	
11:53:25	50	0.11		1												FL150	
11:54:22	20	0.08		1												FL160	
11:55:23	20	0.10		1												FL170	
11:56:19	20	0.09														End of Profile 11 @ FL180	
11:58:30	15	0.08														Start Profile 12 from FL180	
11:59:41	20	0.07														FL170	
12:00:49	55	0.09		1												FL160	
12:01:57	110	0.10		1												FL150	
12:03:12	445	0.10		5												FL140	
12:04:15	1100	0.11		10												FL130	
12:05:22	930	0.11		10												FL120	
12:06:36	670	0.10		5												FL110	
12:07:40	1400	0.11		5												FL100	
12:08:40	1900	0.10		20												FL090	
12:09:31	3800	0.10		20												FL080	
12:10:35	4700	0.12		100	1											FL070	
12:11:38	5500	0.11		100	10											FL060	
12:12:41	6100	0.11		100	60											FL050	
12:14:22	3800	0.10	672	80	70											FL040	
																Word Failed	
12:22:00	3800	0.09	Off	80												In Run 9 @ 2000'	
12:24:00	4500	0.10	Off	80	60												
12:26:00	10000	0.09	Off	80	60												
12:28:00	6000	0.09	Off	80	60												
12:30:00	5100	0.09	Off	80	70												
12:32:00	4300	0.09	Off	80	50												
12:34:00	3500	0.09	Off	80	50												
12:36:00	3500	0.09	Off	80	40												
12:38:00	3300	0.10	Off	80	45												
12:39:21																End of Run 9	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B158

Date: 17/1/2006	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 5
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:40:17	2100	0.10	Off	80	40											Start Profile 13 from 2000'	
12:41:45	1700	0.10	Off	80	45											FL030	
12:43:33	3700	0.10	Off	80	45											FL040	
12:45:00	1300	0.09	Off	20	Noise											End of Profile 13 & Start Run 10 @ FL050	
12:47:00	1500	0.09	Off	20	Noise												
12:49:00	1000	0.08	Off	20	10												
12:51:00	760	0.08	Off	20	Noise												
12:53:00	600	0.09	Off	20	Noise												
12:55:06																End of Run 10 & Start Profile 14 from FL050	
12:56:01	1800	0.09	Off	10	Noise											FL060	
12:57:19	1000	0.10	674	10	Noise											FL070	
12:58:18	610	0.09		5	Noise											FL080	
12:59:05																End of Profile 14 & Start Run 11 @ FL090	
13:00:00	520	0.09		5	Noise												
13:02:00	450	0.10		5	Noise												
13:04:00	530	0.11		5	Noise												
13:06:00	540	0.11		5	Noise												
13:08:00	430	0.11		5	Noise												
13:09:14																End of Run & Start Profile 15 from FL090	
13:10:15	390	0.11		5	Noise											FL100	
13:11:10	255	0.11	675	5	Noise											FL110	
13:12:09	330	0.10		5	Noise											FL120	
13:12:57	220	0.10		5	Noise											FL130	
13:14:13	110	0.09		3	Noise											FL140	
13:15:10	80	0.10		3	Noise											FL150	
13:16:18	75	0.10		2	Noise											FL160	
13:17:20	65	0.10		1	Noise											FL170	
13:18:24	50	0.10		1	Noise											End of Profile 15 & Start Profile 16 @ FL180	
13:19:33	50	0.10		1	Noise											FL170	
13:20:19	80	0.10		1	Noise											FL160	
13:21:18	150	0.10		1	Noise											FL150	
13:22:25	345	0.10		5	Noise											FL140	
13:23:20	350	0.10		5	Noise											FL130	
13:24:16	200	0.10		5	Noise											FL120	
13:25:20	360	0.10		5	Noise											FL110	
13:26:22	495	0.12		10	Noise											FL100	
13:27:15	535	0.12		10	Noise											FL090	
13:28:21	600	0.11		10	Noise											FL080	
13:31:21	620	0.11		10	Noise											FL070	
13:32:19	525	0.11		5	Noise											FL060	
13:33:09	1200	0.09		20	Noise											FL050	
13:34:30	380	0.11		80	Noise											FL040	
13:35:40	330	0.12		80	Noise											FL030	
13:36:23	360	0.12		80	Noise											End of Profile @ 2200'	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B158

Date: 17/01/2006

REPROCESSED BY S OSBORNE 13/3/06

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt	✓	
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	✓	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	✓	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	✓	Note the calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	✓	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	✓	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC -- are they correctly synchronized in time?		interesting FFSSP behaviour between 09:30 to 13:30 in the nevezorov peaks
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B158

Date: 17/01/2006

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	✓	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	✓	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	✓	
4) Log on to FLOODS	✓	
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	✓	
6) In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat iii) exit	✓	Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	✓	
8) 2D image display and printing Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' i) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec	✓	This section is optional Features to look for: 1) Noise on 2D-P – does it affect non-edge diodes (with potential to create spurious particle counts)? 2) Can you identify a dominant particle habit for the whole flight (eg. drops or crystals) 3)

<p>Preparation of imagery for Core data product</p> <p>iii) WAVE> auto_image</p> <p>a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:</p> <p>b) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD</p> <p>d) Enter start time 0 if unknown</p> <p>e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown</p> <p>f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">10</p> <p>iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files</p>		<p>PMSDATA: FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_Bnnn_2Dx-IMAGES.PS</p>
<p>ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC</p>		
<p>Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter</p>		
<p>Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files</p>		
<p>9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn</p> <p>b) Directory: PMSDATA:</p> <p>c) File generation: Hit enter</p> <p>d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data</p>		
<p>e) TAS: Y</p> <p>f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX</p> <p>g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">0 unless either probe known to be faulty</p> <p>h) Start time: 0 if unknown</p> <p>i) End time: 240000 if unknown</p> <p>j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5</p> <p>k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown</p> <p>l) Coefficient choice: 2</p> <p>m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p style="text-align: center; color: blue;">06569 13400</p> <p>Note the particle type</p>
<p>10) In PVWAVE</p> <p>i) enter:</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">!PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]'</p> <p style="padding-left: 20px;">Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important!</p> <p>ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D'</p> <p>iii) exit</p>		
<p>11) MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D</p> <p>b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX</p> <p>c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name</p> <p>d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?</p>		<p style="color: blue;">No H₂O - Check large spike @ ≈ 10:50.</p>

CCN LOG

all @ 1hr.00mins

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	T ₆
10:38:50	10:39:33	FL100	16.4	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	20.16
		✓	15.75	0.52	0.76	1.15	1.51	2.2	S 20.25
			14.83	598	630	754	884	1384	D 20.31
			14.13	216	211	217	233	275	B 20.42
			12.96	2236	2249	2352	2342	2312	R 20.51
				978.6	978.3	978.0	978.0	978.2	P
10:51:17	10:53:40	F65	17.86	0.52	0.75	1.11	1.47	2.14	S 21.56
10:53:02		✓	17.27	1792	3502	3799	3792	4092	D 21.71
			16.3	212	228	228	445	781	B 21.81
			15.62	2265	2317	2361	2349	2316	R 21.86
			14.45	986.9	986.9	986.5	986.5	986.4	P 21.94
11:01:37	11:02:13	FL65	18.59	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S 22.35
		✓	17.91	0.52	0.74	1.13	1.46	2.11	D 22.41
			17.0	2212	3054	3695	4095	4095	B 22.51
			16.32	232	258	258	408	897	R 22.58
			15.15	2260	2248	2247	2251	2255	P 22.67
				986.7	986.5	986.5	986.4	986.5	
11:20:47	11:21:23	2800ft	20.31	0.5	0.72	1.1	1.42		S 24.07
		3	19.62	2206	3155	3795	4095		D 24.12
			17.92	246	266	334	480		B 24.2 ← 3
				2262	2245	2242	2248		R
				986.5	986.4	986.5	986.4		P
11:31:15	11:31:51		21.09	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S 24.87
				0.5					D
				3626					B
				384					R
				2305					P
				986.5					
12:00:33	12:01:06	6000ft	22.38	0.48	0.69	1.06	1.38	1.98	S 26.14
			21.53	2723	3807	4095	4095	4095	D 26.03
			20.50	331	357	477	657	1135	B 25.99
			19.74	2293	2297	2301	2318	2339	R 25.99
			18.53	986.8	986.7	986.5	986.7	986.8	P 26.01
12:11:50	12:12:27	9000ft	22.48	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S 26.23
			21.73	0.48	0.69	1.05	1.36	2.0	D 26.29
			20.69	3127	4095	4095	4095	4095	B 26.11
			19.91	350	378	476	636	964	R 26.15
			18.61	2391	2400	2403	2414	2419	P 26.12
				986.8	986.9	986.7	986.7	986.9	
12:33:52	12:34:32	FL100							S
									D
									B
									R
									P

aborted
knocked off.

aborted
altitude change.

aborted
climb

CCN LOG

*Peak not found largest V seen.

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF		FEET	1	2	3	4	5	
		FL490		1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
12:36:38	12:36:58 12:37:20		23.07	0.48	0.7	1.06	1.34	1.99	S 26.8
			22.24	1913	2732	2782	2080*	4092	D 26.71
			21.26	226	240	306	380	617	B 26.81
			20.47	2400	2397	2386	2382	2366	R 26.75
			19.22	984.3	984.5	984.3	984.2	984.5	P 26.72
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
13:18:32	13:19:06	2000ft	23.39	0.47	0.69	1.02	1.35	1.95	S 27.15
			22.67	2000	3979	4092	4095	4095	D 27.18
			21.65	2296.5	291	399	648	1038	B 27.13
			20.59	264.5	2291	2282	2277	1038	R 27.17
			19.57	986.8	986.7	986.7	986.8	986.8	P 27.07
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
13:26:42	13:27:18	" "	23.3	0.48					S 27.04
				4095					D
				268					B
				2270					R
				986.7					P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
13:31:16	13:31:49	" "	23.52	0.47	0.68	1.03	1.34	1.95	S 27.24
			22.77	1074	1555	2668	3533	3633	D 27.26
			21.77	147	157	175	220	689	B 27.27
			21.03	2282	2296	2297	2287	2285	R 27.27
			19.78	986.7	986.9	986.8	986.8	986.8	P 27.27
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
13:45:00	13:45:37	5000ft	23.77	0.47	0.69	1.04	1.39	1.96	S 27.52
			23.12	157.5	2674	4095	4095	4095	D 27.62
			22.07	1897.5	182	253	385	749	B 27.63
			21.25	2290	2302	2315	2327	2345	R 27.48
			20.00	986.7	986.8	986.7	986.7	986.8	P 27.51
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
13:59:08	13:59:50	9000ft	24.12	0.47	0.68	1.02	1.33	1.94	S 27.9
			23.32	1756	1745	2541	3095	3594	D 27.86
			22.32	175	185	237	285	525	B 27.84
			21.55	2391	2395	2397	2395	2404	R 27.8
			20.27	984.0	984.4	984.3	984.1	984.5	P 27.9
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

aborted
too
response
swamped

open
water

[Handwritten signature]

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.158**

 Date **17/01/2008**

 Operator's name **M. GLEW**

 Page **1** of **3**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks	
Dry Neph Zeroed before flight. Failed to zero wet neph - zero is from 14/01/2008 Many common problems - failure to wet, dry + chiller before take off on addresses ARSL7:INSTR, ARSL8:INSTR and ARSL9:INSTR. Same set up as B157 except wet + dry ports switched. Turned chiller power off - with dry wet neph with water in system but no chiller operation									
0837	preflight		10.2	53%	70%	DRY		w/D ratios \approx 0.9 for all 3 colours	
0900	Take off		10.4						
090056	P1	FL050	10.4	36%	50%	DRY			
090848	P2	50' ↑	10.3	22%	44%	DRY			
092358	P2 Intercept	FL130	10.3	22%	37%	DRY		w/D ratios \approx 0.6	
093010	P3	FL180 ↓	10.9	13%	33%	DRY			
093831	R1	FL100	10.1	20%	36%	DRY			
0944	R1	FL100	10.3	18%	36%	Water		in system, chiller power off	
0949	P4	FL100 ↓	10.9	21%	76%	↑		water set to +30°C	
095104	R2	FL060	10.4	20%	76%	↑			
095300	R3	FL065	10.3	20%	75%				
0958	R3	FL065	10.3	21%	81%	↑		water set to +40°C	
1010	Had several low coolant warnings.								water set to +10°C. wet neph R1 at 90% → 20% → 75% no growth seen.
102045		2200'	10.6	75%	73%	↓	+10°C		
103113	R5	FL050	10.2	34%	70%	T	+15°C	water set to +35. 2 fumes on trap.	

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.158**.....

 Date **17/01/2005**.....

 Operator's name: **M. OLSEN**.....

 Page **2** of **3**...

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
1042	R5	FL050	10-0	47%	86%	↓		water set to +15°C
105853	R6	FL060	9-9	44%	75%			chiller off. 6 fingers water in trap.
1105	R6	FL060	10-2	42%	75%	↑	+20°C	water set to +20°C chiller on.
110854		FL060↑	9-9	30%	74%		+20°C	chiller off in profile.
11110	R7.1	FL080						
1119	R7.1	FL080	10-1	19%	75%	↑		chiller set to +30°C
1126	R7.1	FL080	10-1	20%	81%	T		chiller set to +25°C
113638	R8	FL090	10-0	19%	87%	↓	25°C	water set to +25°C
1141	R8	FL090	10-0	18%	85%	↓	22°C	water set to +15°C
114456	R8end	FL090	10-0	18%	80%	↓		chiller off for ascent.
121832	R9	2000'	10-1	58%	82%	↓	+20°C	Trap drained. chiller on, water to +15°C
1230	R9	2000'	10-0	51%	72%	↑		water to +30°C
1235	R9	2000'	9-9	46%	80%	T		water to +35°C
133930	R9end	2000'	9-9	38%	86%	↑		chiller off for
124500	R10	FL050	10-0	20%	86%	↑	+34	chiller on
1246	R10	FL050	10-0	20%	86%	↓		chiller set to +25°C
1253	R10	FL050	9-9	16%	81%	↓	+23	chiller set to +15°C
125501	R10end	FL050	9-8	16%	78%	↓		
125908	R11	FL090	10-4	18%	74%	↓	+15°C	
1301	R11	FL090	10-4	15%	73%	↑	+20°C	chiller set to +20°C

UPPER SHIMS &		SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET							
Flight #	B 158	Date		Operator(s)	S. Rogers	log page	2	of	3
Time	Run Id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

SHIMS						
10 58 05	↑	FL060	DARK	100	500	OK
10 58 17			DARK	100	500	
10 58 53	R6	FL060				T=16
11 08 54	P8 ↑					
11 09 30			DARK	100	500	OK
11 10 00			DARK	75	400	OK
11 10 13			Scen	75	400	T=19
11 11 10	R7.1	FL080				
11 16 03	R7.2					
11 27 05			DARK	75	400	OK
11 27 52			Scen	75	400	T=18
11 31 00	P9 ↑	FL080				to FL100
11 35 24	P10 ↓	FL100				to FL090
11 36 36	R8	FL090				T=16
11 45		"	DARK	75	400	OK
11 45 41		"	Scen	75	400	T=15
11 47 37	P11 ↑	"				to FL180 ^{correct} alt in signal with alt
11 56 22	P11 end.					
11 56 28		FL180	DARK	75	400	Clear skies above.
11 56 40			Scen	75	400	
11 58 29	P12 ↓					to 2000 ft
12 18 32	R9	2000ft				T=19
12 18 41		"	DARK	75	400	OK
12 18 47		"	Scen	75	400	T=17
12 24 20			DARK	75	400	OK
SWS						
12 25 24	R9	2000ft	DARK	350	100	OK.
12 25 32		174ft	Scen	350		LOTS of variability
						Passing over river
12 30 19			DARK	350	100	OK
SHIMS						
12 31 27	R9	2000ft	DARK	75	400	OK
12 31 35			Scen	75	400	
12 39 54			DARK	75	400	OK
12 40 06			Scen	75	400	
12 40 16	P13	2000				to FL050

MICROTOPS II SUNPHOTOMETER

SHEET NO

1

DATE 17 01 2006 SKY CONDITIONS 2
 OPERATOR D. T. ODEMAN FILENAME ONCE DOWNLOADED
 START TIME 08:00:00

Enter Site Details Below:

Site Name in Full	Abbreviate	Latitude	Longitude	Height above sea level(m)
GENB HOTEL NAME1	NAME1	13.5	21	80

AOD

TIME	SKY	SITE	MTP Scan Number	AOD (380)	AOD(440)	AOD(675)	AOD(936)	AOD (1020)	WV(g/cm ²)
08:00:00	2	NAME1	40	0.503	0.467	0.382	0.327	0.282	1.35
08:27:43	2	"	41	0.463	0.431	0.355	0.298	0.257	1.38
09:03:53	2	"	42	0.427	0.401	0.326	0.272	0.235	1.41
09:56:19	1	"	43	0.452	0.428	0.349	0.291	0.251	1.50
10:14:37	1	"	44	0.565	0.536	0.452	0.409	0.353	
10:14:37	2	"	44	0.565	0.536	0.457	0.409	0.353	1.49
10:59:21	2	"	45	0.640	0.613	0.530	0.495	0.427	1.44
11:23:17	2	"	46	0.626	0.595	0.511	0.470	0.405	1.45
11:37:50	2	"	47	0.714	0.661	0.584	0.567	0.489	1.42
12:41:02	2	"	48	0.689	0.651	0.563	0.547	0.471	1.43
13:13:26	2	"	49	0.670	0.624	0.545	0.495	0.426	1.52
14:43:55	2?	"	50	0.914	0.880	0.801	0.836	0.721	1.37
14:56:49	2	"	51	0.630	0.590	0.484	0.440	0.379	1.49

SKY CONDITIONS: [0] Clear Sky; [1] Haze, [2] Thin cirrus-sun not obscured; [3] Thin cirrus - sun obscured; [4] Scattered cumulus - sun not obscured; [5] Cumulus over most of the sky - sun not obscured; [6] Cumulus - sun obscured; [7] complete cumulus cover; [8] Status- sub obscured; [9] Drizzle.

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B158

Date:

17 JAN 2005

Operator:

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	47 mm Whatman QMA (top)	Bottom inlet	90 mm 0.4 µm Nuclepore followed by a 90 mm paper (top)
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On	Time Off	Flight Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments
Filters run1	B158Q1	----	----	Top	09:38:31	09:46:05	R1	546	FL100, old biomass
Filters run1	B158N1	----	----	Bottom	09:38:31	09:46:05	R1	423	FL100, old biomass
Filters run 2	B158Q2	----	----	Top	09:51:04	10:13:04	R2	1992	FL060, then FL065 from 09:53:00 to be at max aerosol concentration, old biomass
Filters run 2	B158N2	----	----	Bottom	09:51:04	10:13:04	R2	1611	FL060, then FL065 from 09:53:00 to be at max aerosol concentration, old biomass
Filters run 3_a	B158Q3	----	----	Top	10:20:45	10:26:32	R4	529	2800 feet, smoke haze, fires on the ground, maybe some clouds encountered
Filters run 3_a	B158N3	----	----	Bottom	10:20:45	10:26:32	R4	467	2800 feet, smoke haze, fires on the ground, maybe some clouds encountered
Filters run 3_b	B158Q3	----	----	Top	10:27:43	10:43:07	R5	1380	Continuing previous run at FL050 to avoid clouds, smoke haze
Filters run 3_b	B158N3	----	----	Bottom	10:27:43	10:43:07	R5	240	Continuing previous run at FL050 to avoid clouds, smoke haze
Filters run 4_a	B158Q4	----	----	Top	10:58:53	11:08:54	R6	901	FL060 over Ilorin, first of a series of stacked and levelled runs, smoke
Filters run 4_a	B158N4	----	----	Bottom	10:58:53	11:08:54	R6	743	FL060 over Ilorin, first of a series of stacked and levelled runs, smoke haze
Filters run 4_b	B158Q4	----	----	Top	11:11:10	11:26:56	R7.1/R7.2	1296	FL080 over Ilorin, second of a series of stacked and levelled runs, 5 min heading south, then 10 min heading north on a reciprocal, smoke haze
Filters run 4_b	B158N4	----	----	Bottom	11:11:10	11:26:56	R7.1/R7.2	1005	FL080 over Ilorin, second of a series of stacked and levelled runs, 5 min heading south, then 10 min heading north on a

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B158

Date:

17 JAN 2005

Operator:

PFO

									reciprocal, smoke haze
Filters run 4_c	B158Q4	----	----	Top	11:36:38	11:44:56	R8	641	FL090 over Ilorin, third of a series of stacked and levelled runs, top of the aerosol layer around FL100, smoke haze
Filters run 4_c	B158N4	----	----	Bottom	11:36:38	11:44:56	R8	489	FL090 over Ilorin, third of a series of stacked and levelled runs, top of the aerosol layer around FL100, smoke haze
Filters run 5	B158Q5	----	----	Top	12:24:00	12:39:30	R9	1374	2000 feet, intense smoke haze, Fire @122535 returning from Ilorin towards Bani
Filters run 5	B158N5	----	----	Bottom	12:24:00	12:39:30	R9	1258	2000 feet, intense smoke haze, Fire @122535 returning from Ilorin towards Bani
Filters run 6_a	B158Q6	----	----	Top	12:45:00	12:55:01	R10	935	FL050 towards Banizoumbou, old biomass burning or clear slot
Filters run 6_a	B158N6	----	----	Bottom	12:45:00	12:55:01	R10	784	FL050 towards Banizoumbou, old biomass burning or clear slot
Filters run 6_b	B158Q6	----	----	Top	12:59:08	13:09:08	R11	796	FL090 towards Banizoumbou old biomass burning or clear slot
Filters run 6_b	B158N6	----	----	Bottom	12:59:08	13:09:08	R11	621	FL090 towards Banizoumbou old biomass burning or clear slot
Filters run 7	----	----	----	Top	----	----		----	----
Filters run 7	B158AFM1	----	----	Bottom	12:18:32	12:23:00	R9	700	Run at 2000 from Ilorin towards Banizoumbou, exposing a sticky glass dishes mounted on a 90-mm paper filter for individual particle shaping, heavy biomass burning

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 158

Date: 17th January 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	Y
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
“ JN02	N	AMS	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	N		
MARSS	N		
DEIMOS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	N	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	Y
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B158

Date: 17th January 2006

Instruments

1. FFC window becoming dirty – bug smears. Ground Eng informed and will clean at next opportunity
2. FFC Picture black and white only during pre-flight., okay in flight
3. JW – not zeroing, as on recent flights.
4. CCN – Pump shorting out across power supply indicator bulb. Pulled down some of the 240Vac supply. Took the bulb out of the circuit then okay.
5. AMS – went down at 1036. Switch accidentally knocked off by CCN. Will rig up a “kick plate” to cover AMS switches for next flight. Recovered okay and will do a cal after flight.

SHIM / SWS – can only operate one or the other

Cloud Physics – FFSSP only good down to FL80 otherwise okay

Core Chemistry – Okay

CVI – okay

Wet Neph – some leak problems

VACC – u/s

Not fitted: ARIES, MARSS, DEIMOS

Aircraft

1. Aircon Pack 2 u/s as before

Satcom H Calls – 1 made by DFL

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B158:

Log	Reason
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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